

SECURE IMAGE TRANSFER IN THE DOMAIN TRANSFORM DFT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new approach for secure image transmission. It consists of three treatments including: a compression based on Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), a use of symmetric encryption Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and a Data Hidden Insertion technique for the transport of sensitive information.

KEYWORDS

DFT, Cryptography, Watermarking, LSFR, Secure Image Transmission

1. INTRODUCTION

Our research is based on the combination of three methods of information processing. Firstly, the information to be transferred, an image, undergoes a source coding which is a compression of the signal used for the purpose of eliminating all redundancy and optimize the computing power. For this we used the Discrete Fourier Transform on digital information. The use of this mode is that, firstly, the DFT coefficients represent the image as a complex form, which increases the choice of the use of these coefficients and, secondly, it simplifies the matrix representation of the image and reduces the number of calculations and manipulations to do [1].

Secondly, we developed an algorithm for generating random key that is able to provide session keys used to encrypt the information. The encryption algorithm used is AES, this symmetric encryption algorithm is known, used and implemented in various computer systems because of its speed and robustness against various types of known attacks, according to [2]. The encryption system operates only on a part of the information, we use a selective encryption. We therefore chose a part of the representation of the image obtained after the use of the Fourier transform, which represents the coefficients representative of the information, that is to say, the real part of the transform.

Thirdly, for the transport of the session keys, which will be used for decryption, we insert them in the other part of the coefficients, which is the imaginary part. For this, we used an additive watermarking technique because of his resistance to the types of geometric attacks [3]. We present two techniques that differ from each other by their robustness against attacks.

2. PROPOSED APPROACH

At the emission, we have the diagram (Figure 1). At the reception, the restitution of the information is done through a series of reverse operation to that proposed.

Figure 1. Emission Datagram

3. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

As the encryption method used is a symmetric encryption, the same key will still be used for decryption at the receiver. To enable secure sharing of the session key we insert and hide it in another part of the information to be sent. For this, we used a technique for watermarking information. The type of data insertion is based on watermarking robust to compression and geometric transformation such as rotation and translation, explicitly as in [4] and [5]. For this, we chose to use the additive watermarking method.

It should be noted that in the program, we added different techniques of diffusion and confusion to make the algorithm difficult to understand by a cryptanalyst, but rapid at the same time. Series of test are carried out on a personal Computer running with Intel Pentium Dual Core 2.2 GHz with 3072 MB of RAM.

We can see at the Figure 2 that the operation generates a loss of information equivalent to the "peak signal to noise ratio" $PSNR = 31.3674$ dB, a "mean square error" $MSE = 47.4619$ and a "maximum of deviation quadratic" $maxerr = 38.9445$. The method used in this section has been applied in the LSB of each pixel, which is why this method is more robust as we come again to extract the session key after an attack by median filtering and after adding noise type "salt and pepper". This approach does not stand face to geometrical attacks.

Figure 2. Column 1: original image and his histogram, column 2 : crypted-watermarked image and his histogram, column 3 : reconstitute image and his histogram

The correlation between the original image and the reconstructed image is $\text{corr} = 0.9933$, which corresponds to an acceptable result according to its importance [3]. Table 1 shows the effectiveness of the program both on transmission and reception. The implementation of this program is optimized when using on a platform with limited resources such as embedded systems or cameras.

Table 1: Implementation time of the algorithm

	Implementation time	CPU Time
Transmission	0.4315 s	0.4212 s
Reception	0.0829 s	0.0936 s

In a second approach, shown in Figure 3, the operation is done not on the least significant bits, but rather on the set of bits. Therefore, we are faced with much loss of information at reception because we use the low coefficients of the image obtained after the Fourier transform.

Figure 3. Column 1: original image and his histogram, column 2: crypted-watermaked image and his histogram, column 3: reconstitute image and his histogram

We have the following results:

Table 2 : Results obtain

PSNR (dB)	MSE	Maxerr	Corr
7.1407	1.256 e+4	1.364e+3	-0.0028

It should be noted that this second method is not resistant against attacks by scrambling, filters and geometric transformation. After each attack, we do not found the watermark.

Table 3: Implementation time of the algorithm

	Implementation time	CPU Time
transmission	0.6518 s	0.5772 s
Réception	0.1000 s	0.0936 s

The second case differs from the first on the right way to represent the coefficients of the real part of the image compared with the encryption key, that is to say, by choosing to operate on the least significant bits.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Our approach is based on the use of the representation of the image coefficients in complex form as a result of processing by DFT. We have seen that it is advantageous to use a selective treatment of the image especially for the manipulation and representation of the matrix. This approach optimizes the speed in processing time and enables parallelization of the encryption operation and watermarking. This approach is well suited to environments with low material resources and memory space. For robustness, the combination of AES encryption and additive watermarking is more advantageous. AES is often recommended for symmetric encryption and additive watermarking widely used, both are known for their resistance against the types of attacks known and very common.

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